

Spatial Invariance, Information, Fisher Information and Fermat's Least Time Principle

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In (1), we argued that the quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ is a kind of probability which follows from forcing explicit x dependence in a probability function if spatial (translational) invariance exists. In the free particle case, x dependence is forced into $P(x) = dx/L$ i.e. where L is length, i.e. $1/L = A^*A$ where $A = \exp(i f(p,x))$. The relationship $f(p,x)$ then follows from maximizing Shannon's entropy with the constraint $\int g(p) \times P(x)$. This leads to $\exp(i g(p) x)$. Finally, $g(p)=p$, if this function is also to represent maximum p entropy.

The point we wish to make is that in the case of a free particle there are actually two probabilities representing maximum entropy. $P(x)=dx/L$ represents maximum entropy because any dx has equal weight. Forcing a function of x , i.e. $\exp(i f(p,x))$ because of spatial invariance and applying maximum entropy ideas suggests it is treated as a probability as well.

If $\exp(ipx)$ acts in fact like a probability then $\ln(\exp(ipx))$ should represent information. In other words, ipx is information. Here, we try to consider the application of this information in addition to $d/dx \ln(\exp(ipx))$, i.e. use the derivative which appears in Fisher information. In the first case, we argue that in problems involving different possible states (e.g. one dimensional reflection-refraction), different $A \exp(ipx)$ s may appear and add (OR probability). If one insists on the ensuing x -function being continuous together with its first derivative at a translationally invariant x point, this is equivalent to $d/dx \{(A_1 \exp(ipx) + A_2 \exp(ip2x))\}$ at $x_1 = d/dx \{(A_3 \exp(ip3x) + A_4 \exp(ip4x))\}$ at x_1 . This scenario, for example, applies to one -dimensional reflection-refraction. At the same time, one may consider continuity of Information, so the $d/dx \ln(\text{information})$ is really two equations.

Alternatively, one may consider each probabilistic piece separately, i.e. compare an incident photon/particle to a reflected one by itself and argue that in this case $d/dx \text{information} = d/dx ip_1x = d/dx p_2 x$, which then, in fact becomes a conservation law. We argue that Fermat's Least Time Principle is in fact this case. d/dx leads to $d/dx \ln(A_1)=0$, so that probability weights do not come into play because one only considers the px portion, i.e. the conservation law related piece.

We argue that in both cases, d/dx is related to translational invariance in the problem. It is this same translational invariance, however, that led to the form $\exp(ipx)$ as argued in (1). As a result, translational invariance is applied twice. In the first case, a free particle is translationally invariant, in the second, one deals with the translational invariance of an impact point, e.g. an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction interface point.

Translational Invariance and the Free Particle

In (1), we argued that translational invariance is key to developing the quantum free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$. We argued that in general if there is translational invariance, there should exist an explicit x -dependent equation(s). We considered the x independent probability:

$$P(x) = dx/L \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } L \text{ is length}$$

and argued that one may write: $1/L = A^*A$ where $A=A_1 \exp(i f(p,x))$, where $A_1=1$.

Here, translational invariance has nothing to do with a translationally invariant interaction point, because one deals with a free particle.

We then applied the idea of maximum entropy to $\exp(i g(p,x))$ because $P(x)=dx/L$ represents maximum entropy as each dx has the same weight. Maximizing:

$$- \int P(x) \ln(P(x)) + i x g(p) P(x) \rightarrow \exp(i g(p) x) \quad ((2))$$

Finally, we argued that given a $P(x)=dx/L$, one does not know p and so each p has equal weight and there should be maximum entropy in p , suggesting that $g(p)=p$

What emerges from the above argument is that one has two probabilities. The first $P(x)$ is positive and real while the second is complex. According to Shannon's entropy theory $\ln(\text{probability})$ yields a value called information. In the case of $P(x)$, $\ln(P(x))$ yields information about the particle being at a certain x point. Actually, given that the particle is deterministic and one has $x=\text{velocity } t$ (for $x=0$ at $t=0$), $P(x)$ and Shannon's entropy are really linked to time, namely the time the particle spends in each dx unit. In other words, one has a relative type of probability which is normalized to 1 in the length region L .

If one considers $\ln(\exp(ipx))$ one obtains ipx . One may ask: Why does this represent stochastic information. P is a deterministic constant, i.e. momentum, and x is position. Physically, px is information, but $\ln(\text{probability})$ is Shannon's information, and this should make a statement about a stochastic property in the system. We suggest that ipx shows translational invariance in a somewhat different manner than $P(x)=dx/L$, namely through d/dx and $d/dx ipx = ip$ which shows equal weight in space, i.e. constant momentum at each x point. Thus, $d/dx \ln(\exp(ipx))$ is completely consistent with $\ln(P(x))$, but provides physical information about the important quantity, momentum.

We note that Fisher information in statistics is (2):

$$\int f(y,x) \left\{ \frac{df}{dx} \frac{df}{dx} \right\} \quad ((3))$$

It also uses the derivative df/dx , but f is a classical probability, like $P(x)$.

Here we apply d/dx to $\ln(\exp(ipx))$. We note that $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-d/dx$. Without taking d/dx , one does not obtain a constant, i.e. p , representing each x point. This is fine, however, because $\exp(ipx)$ represents a complex periodic x function which has physical implications, i.e. it produces an interference pattern when encountering a 2-slit apparatus if the slits are a wavelength $hbar/p$ apart. This does not change the fact that $\exp(ipx)$ is obtained from $P(x)=dx/L$ and must also contain the information that each dx carries the same weight. Thus, $\ln(\exp(ipx))=ipx$ shows that information changes in space (related to phase shifts etc), but $d/dx \ln(\exp(ipx))$ represents a kind of information that indicates that each dx point is treated in the same manner and is linked directly to momentum. As a result, one sees that due to translational invariance, the translational operator d/dx shows how information changes as one moves from x to $x+dx$, i.e. it doesn't, it is the constant p . This suggests that p represents a

conserved quantity. We will consider this point in more detail later. In other words, given $\exp(ipx)$, one must really consider two kinds of information: $\ln(\exp(ipx))$ and $d/dx \ln(\exp(ipx))$.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

We have suggested above that d/dx information is important for obtaining classical type information when applied to $P_1(p,x)$, i.e. the unusual second probability obtained from forcing x into a probability equation which has no x , yet applies to a translationally invariant problem.

We consider the one dimensional reflection-refraction for a photon moving in the positive x direction and encountering an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction along the y axis at x_1 . The photon may reflect or refract, but the probabilities add to 1. If one writes them in terms of flux/velocity, then:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((4))$$

Here AA (flux written as a quadratic to indicate positivity) represents the incident photon and may be set to 1, BB the reflected and CC the refracted. Nowhere does x_1 appear as the result is translationally invariant. In (1), we suggested that this means one must write an explicit x dependent equation(s). Here there are two unknowns B, C and so two x dependent equations combining to yield ((1)) would solve the problem. By writing $AA/c_1 - BB/c_1 = CC/c_2$ one has a difference of squares.

We have suggested that one may introduce x dependence using $AA \rightarrow A^2$ with $A = A \exp(i f(p,x))$. For a photon $E=pc$ so ((1)) is a kind of pressure balance equation. We argued in (1) that if one chooses $\exp(ipx)$ as the x dependent function, one solves the problem.

The form $\exp(ipx)$, however, follows from translational invariance of a free particle, as argued in section 1, and has nothing to do with an n_1 - n_2 junction. $d/dx \exp(ipx) = ip \exp(ipx)$ is strictly related to the idea that the photon moves in such a way that each x point is treated equally.

If one has two equations involving $\exp(ipx)$ s evaluated at x_1 , there must be a reason for these equations. It is usually argued that one represents continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ s at x_1 and the other, continuity of the first derivative. The two equations are:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2 x) \quad \text{at } x_1 \quad ((5a))$$

$$A p \exp(ipx) - B p \exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x) \quad \text{at } x_1 \quad ((5b))$$

$\exp(ipx)$ is a probability for a free particle (actually $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$), but here one adds probabilities (uses an OR situation). As a result, the LHS of ((5a)) is a new combined probability, but a probability nevertheless. One may immediately ask: Why should one include continuity of the first derivative? Mathematically, this is usually done when joining functions at a point. It is not enough for the function values to match, slope must match as well. This, however, is not a statistical argument and the expressions in ((5a)) and ((5b)) are statistical ones.

In the first section we argued that given x dependent new probabilities linked to a classical, non x -dependent ones (i.e. AA, BB, CC), one should use $d/dx \ln(\text{information})$ to find information about the classical results. If that idea is applied to the one dimensional reflection-refraction

problem, then one would calculate d/dx information on each side of x_1 and equate at x_1 . This leads directly to:

$$d/dx \ln(A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx)) = d/dx \ln(C_2 \exp(ip_2x)) \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is equivalent to ((5a)) and ((5b))

One may then suggest breaking ((6)) into two equations because $\ln(A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx))$ should really be continuous and so $(A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx))$. This begs the question: Why use d/dx at all? There is, however, extra mathematical information in equating a function and its derivative at x_1 as compared to simply equating the function. Thus, d/dx information seems to be important in making a link with the classical probability.

Thus, for the x -dependent probability one applies both (information) and d/dx information to make a link with the classical probabilities.

Conservation of Momentum and Fermat's Least Time Principle

In the above section, we considered the total probability in the one-dimensional reflection-refraction problem which is probabilistic because there may be either reflection or refraction. We pointed out, however, the $\exp(ipx)$ has nothing to do with an n_1 - n_2 junction point, it describes a free particle.

We thus argue that one should be able to use $\ln(\exp(ipx))$ in certain situations which do not make use of an interaction point x_1 , as in the one-dimensional reflection-refraction problem. Nevertheless, this $\ln(\exp(ipx))$, may still be applied to problems that have overall OR probabilities.

As an example, we consider two-dimensional reflection-refraction. The basic argument we use is taken from section 1, namely that $d/dx \ln(\exp(ipx)) = ip$ which shows that all x points are equivalent (in terms of time spent at each). If an interaction junction exists in a problem, overall there will be changes. It is possible, however, that in a certain dimension, namely one linked with translational invariance, one may have no changes in information. As noted, $\exp(ipx)$ is based on free particle spatial invariance. As a result, a change in p would be required to change the probability in a given direction. In the two dimensional reflection-refraction problem, there is no change along the x axis if the n_1 - n_2 junction lies along the x axis at $y=0$. In such a case, $\exp(ip_1(x \text{ component})x_1) = \exp(ip_2(x \text{ component})x_1)$. p_1 and p_2 may differ, but their x -components may be the same. In other words, x -information ip or $d/dx(ipx) = ip$ may be conserved. This may be applied either to the incident-reflected rays alone or the incident-refracted rays. One is not considering overall probabilities with interference.

Using the form $d/dx(ip_1(x \text{ component})x) = d/dx(ip_2(x \text{ component})x)$, however, has consequences. The operator d/dx is used to remove x , as argued in section 1, but is also equivalent to the translational operator. Furthermore, mathematically taking $d/dx F(x)$ and setting it equal to 0 is equivalent to an extremization process. Thus, equivalency of d/dx information may be recast as an extremization problem focused on changing the x point at which the incident ray hits the n_1 - n_2 junction. In other words, d/dx information being constant in

space is equivalent to some kind of extremization in space. The question is: What is being extremized?

We note that if one measures angles from the y-axis, that:

$$p_1(x \text{ component}) \text{ at } x_1 = p_2(x \text{ component}) \text{ at } x_1 \quad ((7))$$

$$p_1 \sin(\theta_1) - p_2 \sin(\theta_2) = 0 \quad \text{where:}$$

$$\sin(\theta_1) = x/\sqrt{xx+YY} \quad \text{and} \quad \sin(\theta_2) = (x-L) / \sqrt{YY+ (x-L)(x-L)} \quad ((8))$$

Here Y is the maximum Y height and L the total x length available.

$1/\sqrt{xx+bb}$, however, is equivalent to: $-d/dx \sqrt{xx+bb}$, where $\sqrt{xx+bb}$ is the length traversed by the ray. This, however, divided by speed is time. So one actually extremizes time, which is Fermat's Least Time Principle.

We note that in the information picture, one may either use $\ln(\exp(ipx))$ or $d/dx \ln(\exp(ipx))$. The operator d/dx removes x, but it is perfectly fine to have $p_1(x \text{ component}) x_1 = p_2(x \text{ component}) x_1$. The x_1 values cancel out automatically and so the derivative d/dx is not explicitly needed. In such a case, there would be no extremization and no least time. Nevertheless, d/dx shows how the information changes in x and so directly links to a physical principle already contained in $P(x)=dx/L$, namely that a particle spends equal time in each dx region. Thus, we do not think that it is simply a mathematical trick to consider d/dx information, for $\text{information}=ipx$, and to link this with extremization in time. d/dx is the translational operator and is directly related to a physical symmetry in the problem. Furthermore, in more complicated situations as described in above sections, $d/dx \ln(\text{information})$ contains more mathematical information than simply $\ln(\text{information})$. It represents two equations, not one.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argued in (1) that $\exp(ipx)$ follows from translational invariance and maximization of entropy for a free particle. Here we consider the Shannon notion of information, $\ln(\text{probability})$. $\ln(\exp(ipx)) = ipx$ which has x dependence while $P(x)=dx/L$ does not. That is fine because there is a periodicity in space and it is physical (phase shifts, two-slit interference). The classical idea of $1/L$ being x independent is also important and we suggest that $d/dx \ln(\exp(ipx))$ indicates this. For $\exp(ipx)$, we suggest one must deal with both $\ln(\exp(ipx))$ and $d/dx \ln(\exp(ipx))$ as important statistical quantities.

In the case of OR (add) probabilities, this leads to two independent equations, as in one dimensional reflection-refraction. One equation may not be enough to solve a problem. Thus, both statistical quantities should be retained. The fact that d/dx information is linked to motion in space suggests it might be linked to other principles in physics. We suggest that even in the case of probabilities for reflection and refraction, one may consider only the case of incident to reflection and incident to refracted, by considering a component in which information does not change.

This should be linked to the conservation of the component of momentum in that direction, namely the translationally invariant direction. One may equate $\ln(\exp(i p(x \text{ component}) x))$ if the x component of momentum is conserved. In principle, $p(x \text{ component}) x$ contains an extra x factor which cancels out at the change point, but using d/dx shows how the information changes in space, and we suggest that this is physically relevant. Thus, we consider d/dx information and show that it leads to Fermat's Least Time principle, which describes motion from one position to another. We suggest that the statistical quantity, information, and d/dx information, which shows how it changes in space, may describe how a particle moves deterministically. In other words, statistics is behind a seemingly deterministic motion (at least in the Fermat's Least Principle case), we argue.

References

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